

D2.4 Geographic data and services inventory

Deliverable number	D2.4.
Deliverable title	Geographic data and services inventory
Nature ¹	OTHER
Dissemination Level ²	PU
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Official submission date:	31/07/2020
Actual submission date:	31/07/2020

¹ **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

² **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Modifications Index	
Date	Version
04/03/2020	0.1
04/07/2020	0.2
18/07/2020	0.3
28/07/2020	0.4
31/07/2020	1.0

This work is a part of the HYPERION project. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CC	Climate Change
ENCA	European Network of Heads of Nature Conservation Agencies
EOS Platform	Earth Observation System
EU	European Union
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
HA	Historic Areas
.dwg	Drawing File
GeoTIFF	Geostationary Tagged Image File Format
.pptx	Power Point File
.shp	Shape File
.xlsx	Excel File

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Executive Summary

This document aims to record all the necessary and available data that are required for the realization of the current project. This is accomplished by creating a list that summarizes the information provided by all stakeholders, especially from open sources. It includes data that has already been gathered as well as data that is still pending.

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1. Introduction

With the ultimate goal of achieving resilience for our historic areas, the accumulation of pertinent data emerges as a critical step. Since it can affect decision making processes and in order to act as a reliable source of information the inventory will have to be as detailed and accurate as possible.

Its creation will serve:

a) the reliable quantification of climatic, hydrological and atmospheric stressors, assisting HYPERION provide quality-assessed numerical indicators. Quantification of the respective stresses on HA elements will be enabled, while processes and interactions from short-term (days) to long-term (10-60 years) timescale climatic scenarios will be covered.

b) the Land Surface model to be used to account for the impact of present and future climate parameters on soil surface, hence quantifying the structural and thermo-physical impacts of the atmosphere and topsoil parameters on HA elements and operations. High-resolution inventorying will allow a resilience assessment platform with a risk modelling interface to be introduced.

c) It will also help HYPERION provide input for the relevant regulatory framework, e.g. Eurocode 1 on load models for climatic actions, that is under revision. Data-based calibration of these load models will be done and methodologies that account for CC will be proposed.

d) Multi-Hazard modelling, which will be extended to cover also indirect CC related hazards (i.e. flooding) as well as geo-hazards (i.e., earthquakes and landslides). Inundation maps will be produced for specific catchments by using the hydrological data collected, while seismic hazards will be quantified. Specific landslide prone areas will also be studied under various precipitation and/or earthquake loads.

e) the on-site Integration, demonstration and validation of HYPERION platform.

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The main purpose of the document is to record all data sources and data services that will be needed during the next phases of the project. This includes the already available files, as well as the ones that are to be collected within the given timeline. Providing all necessary material to the involved project partners for the implementation of their technical deliverables should be highlighted as an additional intention.

Based on the requirements gathered via consultation with users, all the available geographic and other data and services (e.g. hydrological, atmospheric, meteorological) related to CC and various geo-hazards will be catalogued. For each Pilot use, a survey will be conducted on the existing data and services, searching in

similar current or past projects, as well as in relevant research institutions, universities, public bodies, cooperatives and private enterprises. Inventorying will tackle data and services based on either remote-sensing techniques or on-site measurements. It will address all relevant data services, both historical and real-time, including non-free sources. It will be as detailed and accurate as possible exploiting high-quality, efficient GIS applications and products, as well as other database management software (e.g., Hydrognomon free software application for the analysis and processing of hydrological data, mainly in the form of time series, used for floods modelling). Special consideration will be given to open data sources and repositories, accessible through related initiatives (e.g., GEOSS-DataCore, Copernicus, OpenStreetMap, GeoNames, etc.).

1.2 Intended Audience

D.2.4 is a public document. It will be reachable by all stakeholders, Members of the Consortium and the Commission Services. It is particularly interesting for end users, i.e. agencies involved in the management and operation of HA. The HYPERION system can assist their educational purposes and address additional requirements.

2. Dataset Categories

Considering the general scope as well as the specific requirements of the project, specifications for five domains of interest need to be defined. Since each one comprises a dataset category for which meticulous data gathering is critical, a table that summarizes all the required information is generated. The categories for which data information will be presented in this context are: Geometry, Land Use, Vegetation, Hydrology and Satellite.

2.1 Geometry

In order to accurately evaluate historic areas conditions access to detailed designs is necessary. Files containing information about the neighbouring area's topography, the building's 2D & 3D geometry, topological characteristics of all infrastructure utilities as well as their serviceability status should be gathered. Hence, high quality files constructed with essential levels of precision are required and all pertinent data should be recorded in an analytical document. Within the project's scope, the required database consists of the following:

Table 1: Geometry Files

DATA Identification & Availability	Geometry Data Specifications
Dataset description	Inventory, location of the buildings.
Sources	Social geographical information system and accompanying applications of the municipality of Rhodes, Opensource world maps: https://openmaptiles.com/ , Municipality of Rhodes (Directorate of Urban Planning)
Files & Types: SHP	
3D Geometry	3D data for the area of the test sections e.g. in .dwg, .iges, .igs or .stl formats. Any format most CAD programs can read.
Digital Elevation Maps (DEM) SRTM files	Digital Elevation Maps (DEM) for the topography of the test sections under consideration in raster format such as ".geotiff".
Available for Rhodes Pilot Case	
Two separate shape files containing geometry of the	Horizontal Coordinates of each roof of building geometrically defined in two dimensions (x and y coordinates of each point

<p>medieval town and buildings of Rhodes</p> <p>folder: Rhodes</p> <p>files: medieval_town.shp, Rhodes.shp</p>	<p>specified). The third dimension, corresponding to the points' altitude, is not available.</p>
Available for Granada Pilot Case	
<p>Shape File containing geometry of the city:</p> <p>folder: Granada</p> <p>file: Granada.shp</p>	<p>Horizontal Coordinates of each roof of building geometrically defined in two dimensions (x and y coordinates of each point specified). The third dimension, corresponding to the points' altitude, is available.</p>
Available for Venice Pilot Case	
<p>Shape File containing geometry of the city:</p> <p>folder: Venice</p> <p>file: Venice.shp</p>	<p>Horizontal Coordinates of each roof of building geometrically defined in two dimensions (x and y coordinates of each point specified). The third dimension, corresponding to the points' altitude, is available.</p>
Available for Tonsberg Pilot Case	
<p>Shape File containing geometry of the city:</p> <p>folder: Tonsberg</p> <p>file: Tonsberg.shp</p>	<p>Horizontal Coordinates of each roof of building geometrically defined in two dimensions (x and y coordinates of each point specified). The third dimension, corresponding to the points' altitude, is available.</p>
Standards	
<p>Info about metadata (production and storage dates, places) and documentation?</p>	<p>Data can be downloaded from https://openmaptiles.com/ and http://gis.rhodes.gr/rhodes/en/Inspire/tabid/81/Default.aspx. For Tonsberg, the data have been provided by Petra Schneidhofer after personal communication (petra.schneidhofer@vtfk.no)</p>

Standards, format, estimated volume of data	- .shp, Various KB.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the data; copyright holder	Open Source Data
Partner in charge of data collection	AUTH
Partner in charge of data analysis	AUTH
Partner in charge of data storage	AUTH
Related WP(s) and task(s)	WP3, WP4
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Models of the HA under study Information for vulnerability and risk analysis
Data access policy / Dissemination level: Confidential (members of the Consortium and the Commission Services only) or Public	Dissemination level: Public
Data sharing, re-use, distribution, publication	Open source inventory Can be published
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup)	AUTH

In Figures 1,2,3,4 two-dimensional designs of the cities are depicted and the locations of buildings are provided.

Figure 1 Upper: Medieval town of Rhodes, Lower: Buildings of Rhodes

Figure 2 Building geometry (plan view) of Granada

Figure 3 Building geometry (plan view) of Venice

Figure 4 Building geometry (plan view) of Tonsberg

2.2 Land Use

Land uses retain the distinct characteristic of affecting greatly and diversely major projects on multi-scale levels. That being said, the ability to easily and accurately identify, access and update the current land use status of all areas, immediately related or in close proximity, with the cities in question is of great importance. In this context, the availability of the following can be considered crucial:

Table 1: Land Use Data Files

DATA Identification & Availability	Land Use Data Specifications
Dataset description	Land use and land cover maps.
Sources	Opensource world maps: https://openmaptiles.com/
Files & Types: SHP	
Available for Granada Pilot Case	
Openmaptiles.com	Freely available land use dataset.
folder: Granada	
file: Land_use.shp	It contains land use and land cover data for the city of Granada.
Available for Venice Pilot Case	
Openmaptiles.com	Freely available land use dataset.
folder: Venice	
file: Land_use.shp	It contains land use and land cover data for the city of Venice.
Standards	

Info about metadata (production and storage dates, places) and documentation	Data can be downloaded from https://openmaptiles.com/
Standards, format, estimated volume of data	- .shp, Various KB.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the data; copyright holder	Open Source Data
Partner in charge of data collection	AUTH
Partner in charge of data analysis	AUTH
Partner in charge of data storage	AUTH
Related WP(s) and task(s)	WP2 (Task 2.4), WP3
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Feed for climatic and geo-hazards models
Data access policy / Dissemination level: Confidential or Public	Dissemination level: Public
Data sharing, re-use, distribution, publication	Open source inventory Can be published
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup)	AUTH

The following figures are samples of the required data that are part of the category of land use. Figures 5 and 6 constitute illustrations of the indicative format that shape data files have. Such files need to be operated by Geographic Information System applications such as free and open source QGIS. The outputs of such data processing

applications can be like the figures shown below. They demonstrate a variation in land uses on a wider scope, that of the country in which each case study is located.

Figure 5 Land Uses of Granada city

Figure 6 Land Uses of Venice city

2.3 Vegetation

Vegetation's role is critical for achieving every project's sustainability. Table 3 presents the files that have been collected for vegetation.

Table 3: Vegetation Files

DATA Identification & Availability	Vegetation Data Specifications
Dataset description	Vegetation maps of the area surrounding the site.
Sources	Opensource world maps: https://openmaptiles.com/
Files & Types: SHP	
Available for Rhodes Pilot Case	
Vegetation Database folder: Rhodes file: Vegetation.shp	It contains vegetation data for the city of Rhodes
Available for Granada Pilot Case	
Vegetation Database folder: Granada file: Vegetation.shp	It contains vegetation data for the city of Granada
Available for Venice Pilot Case	
Vegetation Database folder: Venice file: Vegetation.shp	It contains vegetation data for the city of Venice
Available for Tonsberg Pilot Case	
Standards	

Info about metadata (production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Data can be downloaded from https://openmaptiles.com/ and http://gis.rhodes.gr/rhodes/en/Inspire/tabid/81/Default.aspx .
Standards, format, estimated volume of data	- .shp, Various KB.
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the data; copyright holder	Open Source Data
Partner in charge of data collection	AUTH
Partner in charge of data analysis	AUTH
Partner in charge of data storage	AUTH
Related WP(s) and task(s)	WP3
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Improve simulations of the climate related hazards on the city.
Data access policy / Dissemination level: Confidential or Public	Dissemination level: Public
Data sharing, re-use, distribution, publication	Open source inventory Can be published
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup)	AUTH

Figures 7 & 8 constitute illustrations of shape data file formats. Such files need to be operated by Geographic Information System applications such as the free and open source QGIS package. The figures shown below demonstrate the vegetation and building layers, respectively, for the Granada pilot case.

Figure 7 Vegetation in Granada

Figure 8 Vegetation in Granada including the buildings

2.4 Hydrology (flood prone areas)

When striving for resilience, the effective management of water on cities is necessary to promote public safety and avoid any kind of disturbance. That's why flood prone areas should be carefully identified and examined. In this context, data for the following fields should be collected:

Table 4: Hydrology Data Files

DATA Identification & Availability	Hydrological Data Specifications
Dataset description	Waterway
Sources	Opensource world maps: https://openmaptiles.com/
Files & Types: SHP files	
Hydrology Data & Flood Hazards	
Available for Granada Pilot Case	
folder: Granada	
Water.shp	Shape files of the waterway of the Granada city.
Available for Venice Pilot Case	
folder: Venice	
Water.shp	Shape files of the waterway of the Venice city.
Standards	
Info about metadata (production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Data can be downloaded from https://openmaptiles.com/ .
Standards, format, estimated volume of data	- .shp, Various KB

Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the data; copyright holder	Open Source Data
Partner in charge of data collection	AUTH
Partner in charge of data analysis	AUTH
Partner in charge of data storage	AUTH
Related WP(s) and task(s)	WP2 (Task 2.4), WP3
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation	Feed for climatic and geo-hazards models
Data access policy / Dissemination level: Confidential or Public	Dissemination level: Public
Data sharing, re-use, distribution, publication	Open source inventory. Can be published.
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup)	AUTH

The following figures are samples of the required data that pertain to the category of Hydrology. Figures 9 and 10 constitute illustrations of shape data files. Such files need to be operated by Geographic Information System applications such as free and open source QGIS. The outputs of such data processing applications can be like the figures shown below. They demonstrate flood prone areas spread inside the city.

Figure 9 Flood Prone Area in the Granada city

Figure 10 Flood Prone Areas in the Venice city

2.5 Satellite

Satellite images have the significant advantage of offering a unique and otherwise unattainable perspective on projects. Thus, when aiming at cultural heritage sites optimization, such technologies have a lot to offer and should be considered.

Table 5: Satellite Data Files

DATA Identification & Availability	Satellite Data Specifications
Dataset description	Satellite images
Sources	Open source https://zoom.earth/
File Types: image files	
Available for all Pilot Cases	
Folder: Satellite_images	
Rhodes.png, Granada.png, Venice.png, Tonsberg.png	Satellite images in png format.
Standards	
Info about metadata (production and storage dates, places) and documentation?	Data can be downloaded as open source from https://zoom.earth/ .
Standards, format, estimated volume of data	- various MB
Partners activities and responsibilities	
Partner owner of the data; copyright holder (if applicable)	Open Source Data
Partner in charge of data collection	AUTH
Partner in charge of data analysis	AUTH

Partner in charge of data storage	AUTH
Related WP(s) and task(s)	WP5
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Observation of the structures of cities
Data access policy / Dissemination level: Confidential or Public	Dissemination level: Public
Data sharing, re-use, distribution, publication	Open source inventory. Can be published.
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	
Data storage (including backup):	AUTH

Figure 11 Satellite image of Rhodes

Figure 12 Satellite image of Granada

Figure 13 Satellite image of Venice

Figure 14 Satellite image of Tonsberg

3. Dataset Sources and Services & Data Management Applications

Attempting to organize the sources from which the project's data got collected, two types of data sources and services were detected. Open Data: considered as sources and services that are publicly open and freely available. Other Data: the ones with confidential data, available only for members of the consortium and the commission services. Additionally, all parties should have access to the data management applications indicated below, for efficient data processing to be enabled.

3.1 OPEN DATA Sources & Services

The following Open Data Sources and Services are necessitated within the project's scope. In the table below, a brief description accompanies each source or service name.

Table 6: Open Data Sources & Services

DATA Sources & Services	Open Data Sources
Dataset description	Public Data: openly available to the public.
Open Sources & Services	
GEOSS-Data Core	The Global Earth Observation System of Systems Platform: links existing observing systems and supports the development of new ones.
Copernicus	European Union's Earth Observation Program: the Copernicus services deliver near-real-time data on a global level, based on satellite and in situ observations.
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
OpenStreetMap	OpenStreetMap is built by a community that contributes and maintains data about roads, trails, cafés, railway stations and more all over the world.
GeoNames	Geographical Database: integrates geographical data such as names of places in various languages,

	elevation, population and other from various sources.
Hellenic Cadastre	System of information that records legal, technical and other details about real estate properties.
Opendata Venice	Considerable amount of data concerning the city.
Social geographical information system and accompanying applications of the municipality of Rhodes	http://gis.rhodes.gr/rhodes/en/Inspire/tabid/81/Default.aspx
Open-source world maps	https://openmaptiles.com

3.2 OTHER DATA Sources & Services

In the category of Other Data, the table that follows lists the required sources and services and provides a brief description for each one.

Table 7: Other Data Sources & Services

DATA Sources & Services	Other Data Sources
Dataset description	Confidential Data: only available for the project.
Sources & Services	
ENCA	European Network of Heads of Nature Conservation Agencies: identifies future challenges and offers information and advice to decision-makers in the fields of nature conservation and landscape protection
EOS Platform (Spot 6/7, Sentinel-2, Landsat 7 ETM+)	Recent, world-class satellite imagery that tracks land changes in real-time. Utilized for purposes of global earth observation, intelligence and security, natural disasters and live events monitoring.

3.3 DATA Management Applications

To enable the efficient analysis of all datasets that are required for the various purposes of this project and to render data processing processes feasible, access to

important computer applications is necessary. In this context, the sole use of openly available applications would facilitate open access and ensure an increase in the accessibility rates of gathered information. However, to simultaneously increase the significance of the project's results other applications, requiring software licenses, are necessitated as well.

Table 8: Data Management Applications

DATA Management Applications	Open and Other Data Management Tools
Open Applications	Openly Available
QGIS	Georeferenced raster and vector data
Palm 6.0	.pdb, .pqa, .prc files Fully parallel
OpenFOAM® v1812	Format generally follows C++ source code Fully parallel
Other Applications	Available with Subscription
AutoCad	.dxf files
Microsoft Office	.docx, .xlsx, .pptx files
ArcGIS 10.4.1 ArcGlobe 10.4.1 ArcMap 10.4.1 ArcScene 10.4.1	Georeferenced raster and vector data Geodatabase data formats File-based data types - DBMS data
ANSYS 18 CFX 18 CFD Post ANSYS 18 ICEM CFD 18	Running under one license – fully parallel .wbpj, .cfx, .cmdb files
MEMO	MEscale AUTH – LHTEE in-house code (black box) MOdel

MIMO	Microscale AUTH – LHTEE in-house code (black box)	MOdel
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4. Conclusions

The purpose of the current deliverable was to record and document all data sources and data services that will be needed during the implementation phases of the HYPERION project. Towards the ultimate goal of achieving resilience for cultural heritage sites, the collection and standardization of pertinent data comprises a critical step. Attention has been given to provide access to both primary data and meta-information in the most consistent and accessible way possible, with the aim to minimize any additional documentation effort in the later stages of the project and to avoid interpretation errors.

In this document, datasets of structural, thermophysical and climatic parameters mainly provided by open sources have been described and annotated. These include maps of surface parameters like high-resolution elevation and land use maps, building geometry and features, as well as thematic layers of climatic, hydrological and geotechnical risk factors. The pertinent data sources, formats and intended users have been documented. Based on the requirements gathered via consultation with users, all the available geographic and other data and services have been catalogued. These data sources will be used for the reliable quantification of climatic, hydrological and atmospheric stressors, assisting HYPERION in providing relevant numerical indicators and implementing multi-hazard modelling.

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